

Forced-Convection Cooling Using a Vortex Tube for Cylinder Shape Metal

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(2022)

Abstract—This experimental paper aims to measure the cooling time and associated effects for steel and aluminum with a cylindrical shape. This experimentation is done by using a small-size vortex tube experimental kit from Meech with the GREEN generator. The work has been done as a part of my Bachelor of Engineering Honours degree during my honors project in 2021-2022. A study about the position of the thermocouple for better accuracy has been carried out. The comparison of two metals from the same dimension and shape has also been done with a large CFD analysis of air behavior around the shape using the Ansys Fluent CFD tool.

Index Terms—Vortex Tube, Ranque-Hilsch, Thermodynamics, Heat Transfer, CFD, Fluid Mechanics

I. INTRODUCTION

A vortex tube, also called a Ranque-Hilsch tube, is an instantaneous thermodynamic system. By applying compressed air at ambient temperature and pressure of about 7 to 8 bar at the inlet, the vortex tube produces two air flows at different temperatures instantly [1]. The first one is colder and the second one is hotter than the inlet [2]. Vortex tubes are widely used in industry for local cooling especially to cool down data servers, electronic devices, or highly explosive atmospheres. Vortex tubes are cheap, low in maintenance cost, and highly reliable due to no moving parts. The vortex tube used was the experimental kit of Meech with the GREEN generator [3], two cylinders of the same shape and size from aluminum and stainless steel, and two thermocouples (fig.1).

II. THERMOCOUPLE POSITION OPTIMISATION

Before starting the experiment, the position of the thermocouples needed to be determined. To achieve that, a set of measurements with one thermocouple under the cylinder and one behind the cylinder has been carried on. The thermocouples were linked to the software Squirrel View to collect the data and export it in CSV for further post-data treatment. The stainless steel cylinder has been heated at 75°C with an oven and cooled down until room temperature around 18°C (fig.2). Both ways seem to be similar. The "under" position has been chosen due to the sandwich position between the cylinder and the insulated

Fig. 1. Experimental Set-up

layer which makes it less sensitive to outside perturbation. These outside perturbations can be visualized in the CFD part further in the paper.

Fig. 2. Thermocouples Position

III. COOLING TIME OF CYLINDERS

The temperature can be from the range of a few degrees to 200°C such as surface powder coating temperature [4]. The parameters used were the same as the thermocouples

position optimization. The outlet parameters at the cold side of the vortex tube used to cool down the cylinders were -28°C and 1.9 m/s . The vortex tube has been placed at 3cm from both cylinders. The cooling time of both aluminum and stainless steel cylinders has been plotted (fig.3). The aluminum one is cooled faster than the stainless steel due to its higher specific heat value. The same exponential decay trend is seen between the two cylinders. This experimental study shows that you can cool at a relatively correct time scale of a few minutes per metal part. Even if 75 degrees seems to not be excessive, it remains that this temperature is easily above many processes.

Fig. 3. Cooling time of the Cylinders

IV. CFD ANALYSIS

Understanding the air behavior at a macroscopic level is useful to determine the better way to cool the object such as its position, tilt, or shape. There are different ways to achieve that by putting smoke [5] or doing a CFD analysis by computer [6]. The simulation used was Ansys Mechanical 2022 with fluent 3D code. This paper is also aimed at understanding and visualizing the behavior of gaseous fluids, the air in that case around a shape. For this simulation, a higher speed (22 m/s) and -46°C has been used to have a better understanding of the situation with the worst conditions. Even with this velocity, the turbulent regime has not been crossed [7], which means that it behaves the same way but with different ranges and magnitudes for the desired calculated parameters. An adaptive mesh grid has been used for better accuracy where events have high magnitudes. and bigger mesh when events have less magnitude to allow an optimized calculation time. A Boolean subtraction has been made to separate a virtual box (corridor of the air stream) and the cylinder. The properties of aluminum have been used for calculations.

The evolution of the axial velocity (fig.4) by vectorial arrow representation has been simulated. The flow which hits the center of the shape projection loses more energy

Fig. 4. Axial Velocity Vector

than particles that hit the border of the shape projection and then lose more velocity. For the vorticity magnitude pathline (fig.5, darker is the color, lower is the vorticity magnitude). When the air hits the cylinder, the direction and velocity change drastically which allows particle pathlines or trajectories to cross each other. When many particles do not go in the same direction, the resultant of the vectors make a rotational flow and then allow a non-zero vorticity vector [8]. When the fluid changes direction around the edge, the vorticity magnitude is much more important.

Fig. 5. Vorticity Magnitude

The particle trajectory by ID (fig.6) represents every particle with a given ID and a different color to see the displacement during the process. Vorticity magnitude has a similar pattern compared to the ID particle pathline. When there is an edge in the front or the back, the trajectory changes brutally and a small region has turbulent characteristics. The dynamic pressure (fig.7) around the cylinder is linked to the velocity by having the same pattern. At the extremity of the projected surface, when the speed is at its maximum in contact with the cylinder, the dynamic pressure is maximum. Behind the cylinder

when the particle changes speed, the dynamic pressure drops and the rear zone has a lower dynamic pressure.

Fig. 6. Particle ID Trajectory

Fig. 7. Dynamic Pressure

V. CONCLUSIONS

This experimentation showed that small industrial parts with a cylindrical shape can be cool at a reasonable time scale from a high temperature to an ambient temperature. The position of a thermocouple has a very small influence on the measurement for such conditions. It is well known that forced convection is much faster than natural convection in exchanging energy. The higher the speed, the higher the exchange rate, and the shorter the cooling time. At this range of temperature and velocity, the overall regime is laminar. It is also well known that a turbulent regime allows a better heat transfer rate than a laminar regime. The dynamic pressure is lower behind the cylinder than in the front or at the surface. Other shapes may behave differently.

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